

Measuring the impact of Rural-to-Urban Migration on Food Security in Algeria During the Period (1970-2023) Using Threshold Models

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Abstract:

This study aimed to analyse the impact of rural migration on food security in Algeria during the period (1970-2023), through the use of Threshold Models, where the results showed that the nature of the relationship between economic variables changes according to different levels of migration, and it was found that rural migration, expressed by the ratio of rural population to the total population, has a significant impact on the food production index, where high levels of migration lead to a decline in agricultural productive capacities, due to the loss of rural labour and erosion of agricultural lands near cities due to urban expansion, on the other hand, the impact of other economic variables (inflation, cultivated areas, import volumes) varies according to each threshold, reflecting the complex and intertwined nature of the impact of migration on food security

Keywords: Rural-urban migration, agricultural output, food security, threshold regression models.

1. Introduction:

Food security is one of the most prominent strategic challenges facing countries in the modern era. It is no longer just a developmental or economic issue, but has become a geopolitical weapon equivalent to military weapons, as countries that have the ability to secure the basic food need for their people are more independent in their political decisions and less vulnerable to international pressures and global crises. The importance of this concept has been particularly highlighted in light of the repeated crises the world has witnessed in recent decades, from foodprice fluctuations, to the repercussions of climate change, to the COVID-19 pandemic, and finally the Russian-Ukrainian war, which exposed the fragility of global food supply chains. Food security is no longer only an economic indicator of development, but has become a tool of control and domination, used to pressure governments and blackmail people by controlling food resources. Therefore, countries that are unable to secure the food of their people are permanently exposed to instability, whether at the political, social or even security level, as hunger has become a tool to ignite chaos and destabilisation, so building a comprehensive national strategy to achieve self-sufficiency and reduce foreign dependence in food is asovereign issue in the first degree, requiring exploiting all available agricultural and human potentials, in addition to promoting sustainable production and consumption patterns.

Hence the importance of food security, which is no longer an economic luxury but has become a pillar of national security for countries.

On the other hand, internal migration from rural to urban areas poses a major challenge to food security. as it is a population movement that carries with it many economic, social and environmental repercussions, foremost among which is the profound impact on the national food security system. This phenomenon leads to a decline in agricultural production as a result of the migration of labour from the fields to urban centres in search of better job opportunities and services. With the increasing concentration of the population in cities, the demand for food increases while the ability to meet these needs locally decreases, which increases dependence on food imports in light of the deficit in local production. This highlights the imbalance between rural and urban areas. While rural areas are a natural reservoir for food production, the exodus of their populations deprives them of this function and turns cities into consumption centres incapable of production. The neglect of rural areas and declining investment in agricultural infrastructure exacerbate this problem, especially in developing countries that suffer from imbalances in the geographical distribution of population and resources. In the case of Algeria, this problem is clearly evident, as urban expansion at the expense of agricultural land has led to a decline in the agricultural sector's contribution to Gross Domestic Product, despite the country's considerable potential. This calls for effective policies to stimulate stability in rural areas and develop agriculture to ensure food sustainability.

In light of rapid demographic changes, rural-urban migration is one of the most significant demographic phenomena that has directly affected the geographical distribution of the population, land use, and food production structures. This migration poses fundamental challenges to efforts to achieve food security, especially given Algeria's partial reliance on local agriculture to meet its food needs. This raises questions about the extent to which these demographic shifts affect agricultural production and self-sufficiency, and the extent to which cities can absorb this population influx without damaging the national food system. This is where the main problem of this study comes in:

How does internal migration from rural to urban areas affect food security in Algeria, and how can a balance be achieved between urban development and the preservation of agricultural production capacity?

Research hypotheses: To answer the main question, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

- Migration from rural to urban areas leads to the neglect and abandonment of large areas of agricultural land, contributing to a decline in local agricultural production and food security levels in Algeria.
- Population pressure on cities resulting from internal migration contributes to the erosion of agricultural land surrounding urban centres, leading to a reduction in cultivated areas and higher food prices, thereby exacerbating food insecurity.
- Unbalanced development policies between rural and urban areas are fuelling migration to cities, weakening the contribution of rural areas to national food security and widening the gap between food supply and demand.

Significance of the study: The significance of this topic lies in the fact that it highlights one of the biggest challenges facing Algeria in the medium and long term, namely the balance between population development and food production capacity. This research also highlights the importance of linking population policies and agricultural policies, and calls for a review of current development trends in order to ensure food security as a strategic goal of national sovereignty.

Study objectives: Through this study, we aim to present the different concepts of rural-urban migration and food security, and to clarify the impact of this migration on local food security. The research also aims to build a quantitative model to measure the impact of internal migration on food security during the period (1970-2023). Through this research, we also seek to provide recommendations to limit the effects of migration on agricultural production and achieve a balance between rural and urban areas, in addition to proposing sustainable development policies that restore the vital role of rural areas in achieving food security.

Previous studies:

- Yang, L. D. ., & Xing, C. K. (2022). Rural Urban Migration and Food Sustainability in China. *Journal of Agriculture & Environmental Sciences*, 6(1), 61–70:

This study sought to examine the impact of rural-urban migration on food sustainability in China, adopting a descriptive research design. The researchers collected data using questionnaires and analysed the data using descriptive and inferential statistics.

The researchers found that rural-urban migration has a negative impact on food sustainability in China because it reduces the labour force in the agricultural sector, thereby negatively affecting economic development and food sustainability. In this way, rural-urban migration threatens food security through reduced agricultural production. The study also pointed out that factors influencing migration include the availability of better social facilities, good schools and hospitals, and recreational facilities in urban areas.

The study recommended the development of policies aimed at reducing rural-urban migration by raising per capita income in rural areas through investment in agriculture. The government should also provide adequate technical products and advisory services, and offer subsidies to achieve significant progress in the agricultural sector. In addition to all this, government and non-governmental agencies should make greater efforts to raise public awareness of the adverse effects of rural-urban migration on food security (Yang & Xing, 2022).

- Jiji, M. M., Audu, I., & Magaji, A. M. (2025). The Impact Of Rural-Urban Migration On Food Security In Gombe Metropolis, Gombe State, Nigeria. *Journal of Political Discourse*, 3(1), 232–239:

This study investigates the impact of rural-urban migration on food security by analysing how population shifts affect agricultural productivity, food availability, affordability, and accessibility in both rural and urban areas. Based on qualitative research interviews, data was collected from both rural and urban respondents to understand migration patterns, drivers, and the consequences on local food supply chains.

Findings reveal that rural-urban migration leads to labour shortages in agricultural communities, reducing food production and exacerbating rural poverty. Simultaneously, results

show that the increasing urban population heightens demand for food, driving up prices and making nutritious food less accessible for low-income households. The study highlights key policy challenges, including the need for improved rural development programs, investment in sustainable urban food systems, and strategies to enhance agricultural resilience.

This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on migration and food security by providing evidence-based recommendations to policymakers on how to balance rural development, urban planning, and food sustainability. In the same way, the researchers emphasize the urgency of integrated policies that address migration-induced food security risks to ensure stable food systems in both rural and urban areas of Gombe State and beyond (Jijji, Adu, & Magaji, 2025).

- Iordaah Sedoo, Agba Solomon Arumun, and Nwafor Solomon. 2019. Effect of Rural-Urban Migration on Food Security of Rural Households in Kwande Local Government Area of Benue State. *Asian Journal of Advances in Agricultural Research* 9 (4), 1–9:

This study investigated the effect of rural-urban migration on food security of rural households in kwande local government area of Benue State, Nigeria. Using multistage sampling technique and a semi-structured questionnaire as instrument, the study revealed the major causes and determined the effect of rural-urban migration of the food security of Kwande local government area and suggested measures to reduce the rate of rural-urban migration.

Through this study, the researchers accepted the hypothesis which states that factors such as search for job, quest for skill acquisition, search for better education, quest for marriage, insecurity, social amenities, and natural disasters are the determining factors of rural urban migration. Therefore, the study concluded that reduction rural-urban migration and improvement in food security are dependent on these factors.

Based on the effects of rural-urban migration, it was recommended that government/policy makers come up with policies that would lead to increased rural development, agricultural mechanisation and rural area development as a measure to ensure food security in rural areas (Iordaah, Agba, & Nwafor, 2019).

- Usman, I. (2025). Effect Of Rural-Urban Migration on Agriculture and Food Security in AWE Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Multi-Disciplinary Research and Development Journals Int'l*, 7(2), 136–150:

The study assessed the effect of rural-urban migration on agriculture and food security in Awe LGA, Nasarawa state with specific emphasis on the push factors driving rural-urban migration on agricultural productivity and food security in the area. The study used neo-Malthusian theory as its theoretical framework and adopted cross-sectional survey design/multistage sampling technique and used questionnaire as the instrument for collection of primary data.

The study discovered that certain factors such as the level of insecurity like the recent upsurge of kidnapping as well as the desire for gainful employment, natural disasters like flood are responsible for the rise in rural-urban migration in the area. The study also discovered that rural-urban migration has effect on agricultural activities and food security in Awe L.G.A.

The study recommends gathering of information about the migrant coming in and out of the LGA for agricultural activities and enforcement of laws (forest guards) prohibiting invasion by herdsmen into farmlands in Awe L.G.A(Usman, 2025).

2. General concepts of rural migration and food security:

2.1. Definition of rural-urban migration

Sociologists and anthropologists use the term migration to refer to the geographical movements of individuals or groups. Migration is defined as the permanent or temporary movement of individuals to places where they can find a livelihood. These places may be within or outside the country's borders, and migration may be voluntary or involuntary (Al-Qasir, 1992, p. 105). Others have defined it as a permanent or semi-permanent change of residence, regardless of the distance travelled, without regard to whether the migration is voluntary or forced, or the distinction between internal and international migration (Abreu, 2012). Based on this definition, it can be said that migration is the movement of individuals from one area to another, whether within the borders of a country (internal migration) or outside it (external migration). Migration may take place through legal or illegal means.

Internal migration, or migration from rural to urban areas, is a response to factors that influence the attractiveness of urban life compared to rural life (such as improved income, quality of education or availability of health services in cities, or negative income shocks in rural areas)(Selod & Shilpi, 2021, p. 8).

2.2. Motives for migration from rural to urban areas:

Through the various definitions of migration mentioned above, it is clear that this phenomenon is not merely a spatial movement of populations, but rather a natural response to the developmental imbalance between rural and urban areas. Cities have become powerful magnets due to the concentration of job opportunities, improved living standards, and the availability of basic, educational, and medical services, in contrast to the deterioration or limited availability of these factors in rural areas. Rural migration is therefore the result of a complex set of economic, social, and environmental factors. Below, we list the most important of these motives:

- Search for employment opportunities: Under the Harris-Todaro model, economists considered internal migration to be a fundamental response to differences in labour market opportunities between regions, with high incomes in urban areas acting as a pull factor for rural residents. Many empirical studies have focused on estimating the role of labour market differences between urban and rural areas(Selod & Shilpi, 2021, p. 8). In most countries, cities are the hubs of factories and administrations, and thus employment opportunities in the industrial and service sectors grow. Therefore, the factors that attract rural residents to cities are the search for jobs with relatively high wages.

- The difference in the standard of living between the country of origin and the country of destination. The difference in income between the two countries increases individuals' desire to migrate, because if an individual's living conditions are good, they will not migrate. The

lower the standard of living, the more individuals will be inclined to migrate (Thunoon Younes, 2014, p. 160).

- Political pressures, military conflicts, economic policies pursued by successive governments, and the lack of attention paid to young people by these governments were also among the reasons that led to the exacerbation of youth migration (Djehglaf, 2020, p. 105). Insecurity in rural areas resulting from conflicts, violence, and social chaos is an important factor in internal migration, as rural areas lack adequate protection due to the concentration of most security centres in cities. This situation leaves villages vulnerable to danger and unrest, prompting their inhabitants to seek safety in cities.

- Weak infrastructure: Weak infrastructure in villages and rural areas is one of the main motives of migration to cities. The lack of reliable transport networks, inadequate water and sanitation services, and declining health and education services are serious obstacles to local social and economic growth and increase rural residents' sense of insecurity and lack of opportunities. In contrast, cities offer a more stable and developed infrastructure environment, with concentrated education, healthcare and transport services, making them an ideal destination for people seeking a better standard of living and greater development opportunities (Deshingkar & Grimm, 2004, pp. 22-23).

2.3. Definition of food security:

The term food security emerged and became widely used with the onset of the global food crisis between 1973 and 1974, which led to a rise in global food prices. As a result, the concept of food security developed significantly, giving rise to several definitions, including:

- The World Food Summit in 1996 stated that food security is achieved when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life (Food Security Cluster Handbook, 2023).

- The World Bank also defines food security as: "the ability of all people at all times to have access to sufficient food for their activity and their community. Food security is achieved in a country when its marketing and trade systems are able to provide all citizens with adequate food at all times, even in times of crisis, global production decline, and adverse international market conditions" (Ben Nasser, 2005, p. 11).

- The Economist Maxwell considers food security to be a complex and evolving concept. Its definition has shifted from a focus on food production to food availability, then to household food entitlement and access, and most recently to a livelihood perspective (Maxwell, 1996, p. 56). According to Amartya Sen, hunger and famine do not necessarily occur because of a shortage of food, but rather because individuals are unable to access it due to a lack of economic or legal means to obtain food. Therefore, food security is not limited to the availability of food, but requires individuals to have the ability to obtain it through what is known as an entitlement system, which includes rights, resources, labour, and market exchanges (Amartya, 1981, p. 1).

Based on the above, it can be said that food security is a flexible concept with a long history and multiple uses. It can be usefully defined as a state in which all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life. It is not only about food supply, but also about access and entitlement.

2.4. Dimensions of Food Security:

According to the aforementioned definitions, food security has four important and necessary dimensions: availability, access, utilisation, and stability. Any imbalance in one of these dimensions negatively affects the other dimensions, thereby weakening food security. Therefore, achieving food security requires balance and integration between all these components, which highlights the interrelated nature of food security and the need to adopt a comprehensive approach to address it. The following figure illustrates the interrelationship between these four dimensions:

Figure 1: Dimensions of Food Security

Source : (Mahindra, Radin, & Shamila, 2021, p. 2)

- Food availability: Food availability addresses the supply side of food security and is determined by food production levels, stock levels, and net trade (Food And Agriculture Organization, 1996, p. 1). This dimension refers to the possibility of having sufficient quantities of food to meet the nutritional needs of the population through domestic production, strategic stocks and net trade. It is not limited to abundance alone, but extends to balanced geographical distribution to ensure that food reaches all groups and regions.

- Access to food: This depends on two main pillars: *Economic access* which is determined by individual income, food prices, and the state's contribution to social support. *Physical access* is determined by the availability and quality of infrastructure such as ports, roads, railways, and food storage that facilitate the movement and functioning of market (Food And Agriculture Organization Of The U.N., 2013, p. 20).

- Utilisation of Food: The way in which the body utilises nutrients from consumed food products, particularly protein, vitamins, and micronutrients, and the ability to effectively utilise these nutrients (Clapp, Moseley, Burlingame, & Termine, 2022, p. 3).

- Food stability: This refers to the stability of the other three dimensions over time. All members of the population must always have access to sufficient food in order to achieve food security. Individuals should not be unable to obtain foodstuffs and products due to sudden problems such as wars, international conflicts, economic and climate crises, or health crises.

The concept of food stability therefore refers to the availability of food and access to it for all individuals (Garcia-Diez, Gonçalves, Grispoli, Cenci-Goga, & Saraiva, 2021, p. 2).

2.5. The impact of rural-urban migration on food security:

The movement of individuals from one place to another inevitably has multiple economic, social and environmental impacts, especially when this movement takes the form of rural-urban migration, which causes structural and demographic changes that lead to complex challenges in food provision and sustainability. The movement of large numbers of people in search of employment opportunities and a better life from rural areas characterised by poor infrastructure, low-income levels and scarce employment opportunities to cities characterised by diverse economic activities and improved health and education services leads to changes in agricultural production and food distribution. Accordingly, the effects of this migration on food security vary between positive and negative, and each of these effects will be discussed below:

- Decline in agricultural production in rural areas: As people move from rural to urban areas, the number of workers in the rural agricultural sector decreases, leading to a decline in agricultural production. Concurrent factors such as climate change, poverty and instability in land ownership also led to a decline in production, putting pressure on local food supplies and increasing dependence on imports. Families that lose some of their members see a decline in their agricultural productivity due to a shortage of labour in this field. This labour may be compensated for by children and women, but it is insufficient. This leads these families into poverty (Food And Agriculture Organization, 2018, p. 80).

- Rapid urban expansion and population growth in cities are putting pressure on food supply systems, leading to difficulties in food provision, rising prices, and widening the gap between supply and demand. This is prompting countries to increase food imports, which has a direct negative impact on the trade balance, as it leads to an increase in the trade deficit when import bills rise. Furthermore, the fragility of food security linked to external markets may threaten political stability, as the state becomes vulnerable to global price fluctuations or export restrictions from exporting countries, which may be used as leverage to influence public interests and national policies.

- The increase in the city's population due to migration from rural areas to urban areas leads to an increase in demand for housing and urban services, resulting in horizontal expansion of cities in what is known as 'urban sprawl,' which often leads to the erosion of fertile agricultural land surrounding or near urban centres. Unplanned urban expansion consumes vast areas of highly productive agricultural land every year, posing a direct threat to countries' ability to secure their food supply from local production. The shrinking of agricultural areas and the rising cost of production and transport lead to higher food prices in urban markets, especially given the high demand caused by rapid population growth in cities.

3. Measuring the impact of rural migration on food security in Algeria during the period (1970-2023) using the threshold model:

3.1. Model variables and data sources:

Independent variables: These variables were:

- The ratio of the rural population to the total population, symbolised by the code (RUMIG), to express migration from rural to urban areas (Rural Migration), which was used as

an approximate indicator of rural migration, such that a decrease in the ratio of the rural population to the urban population reflects the movement of people from rural to urban areas. This indicator is a suitable substitute in the absence of accurate data on internal migration and is used in many economic and demographic studies.

- The Inflation rate (INF) is used to measure the impact of price fluctuations on purchasing power and food production costs, which directly affect food security.

- The Agricultural Land Area (ALA) was also used as an indicator of local agricultural production capacity, as it is one of the decisive factors in achieving food self-sufficiency.

- The Food Import Index (FII) expresses the extent to which the economy depends on foreign countries to meet its food needs, making it an important factor in explaining fluctuations in food security in the face of trade shocks or global price fluctuations.

Dependent variable: The variable expressing food security is represented by the Food Production Index (FPI), which is used as a measure of food security because it reflects the local capacity to provide food sustainably. This index is widely used in economic literature as an indirect indicator of food availability, which is one of the fundamental dimensions of the concept of comprehensive food security, especially in developing countries that rely on local production to meet their food needs.

3.2. Study model:

To assess the relationship between rural-urban migration and food security, we will use threshold models to measure the impact of rural migration thresholds on food security in Algeria. The following model has been formulated:

$$DFPI_t = \begin{cases} \beta_{0,1} + \beta_{1,1}RUMIG_t + \beta_{2,1}INF_t + \beta_{3,1}ALA_t + \beta_{4,1}FII_t + \varepsilon_t & si RUMIG \leq k \\ \beta_{0,2} + \beta_{1,2}RUMIG_t + \beta_{2,2}INF_t + \beta_{3,2}ALA_t + \beta_{4,2}FII_t + \varepsilon_t & si RUMIG > k \end{cases}$$

$$D = \begin{cases} 1 & si RUMIG \leq k \\ 0 & si RUMIG > k \end{cases}$$

Where:

FPI represents food security, RUMIG represents rural-urban migration, INF represents the inflation rate, ALA represents cultivated area, FII represents the import volume index, K represents the threshold value for food industries, D represents a conditional variable, and u_t represents random error.

If RUMIG is less than or equal to the threshold level K, then D equals zero, but if RUMIG is greater than the threshold level K, then D equals one.

3.3. Results of the threshold regression model (TAR) assessment to measure the impact of rural-urban migration on food security in Algeria during the period 1970-2023:

Table 1: Estimation of the threshold regression model

		RUMIG>53.81%	44%<RUMIG<53.81%	33.90%<RUMIG<44%	RUMIG<33.9%
C	Parameter	-31.069	209.127	-30.299	-224.1419
	probability	0.2404	0.0002	0.7611	0.0000

	Elasticity	-0.1545	0.8914	-0.1399	-1.1943
RUMIG	Parameter	0.99	-1.0470	-3.750	-4.875
	probability	0.0796	0.0002	0.0003	0.0000
	Elasticity	0.2879	-0.2158	-0.6674	-0.7455
INF	Parameter	-0.168	0.1930	0.771	-0.9
	probability	0.19	0.0101	0.0000	0.0198
	Elasticity	-0.0071	0.0142	0.016	-0.0257
ALA	Parameter	-0.292	-8.030	13.981	26.171
	Probability	0.5853	0.0083	0.0034	0.0000
	Elasticity	-0.0263	-0.5605	1.0945	2.4148
FII	Parameter	0.153	0.102	-0.530	0.17597
	Probability	0.0089	0.411	0.0077	0.0007
	Elasticity	0.0071	0.0097	-0.0715	0.0731
R²=0.9962		F-statistic=477.21	Prob(F-stat) =0.0000		Durbin-Watson=1.7629

Source: Prepared by researchers.

The results of the threshold model estimation show that there are four thresholds for explaining agricultural output in terms of each of the following indicators: rural-urban migration, inflation, cultivated area, and import volume.

First threshold: where the ratio of rural population to total population exceeds 53.81%. At this threshold, we observe that the impact of rural migration is positive, such that for every 1% increase in the rural population, the food production index increases by 0.2879%, which is statistically significant at the 10% level. If this indicates anything, it indicates that the increase in the rural population enhances local agricultural activity through the availability of agricultural labour, the expansion of cultivated areas, and the stability of rural communities in production areas. It also contributes to increased plant and animal production, which raises the food production index and thus provides food, which is a contributing factor to food security. This was the economic situation after Algeria's independence, when most of the population lived in rural areas and each family produced its own food requirements and often sold what it did not need. This was the state's objective through its rehousing and rural development programmes and policies, but these programmes failed.

We also note that the impact of inflation at this threshold was negative, which seems logical, as inflation affects the purchasing power of citizens and thus affects the prices of agricultural inputs (such as fertilisers, fuel, equipment and veterinary medicines). This reduces farmers' ability to purchase them, in addition to the high cost of marketing their products, which negatively affects production and leads to a reduction in production or an increase in prices. This is what Algeria has experienced and continues to experience due to weak infrastructure in rural areas and a lack of support for the agricultural sector. Thus, a 1% increase in inflation leads to a 0.0071% decrease in food security, which is consistent with economic theory and reality.

We also note that an increase in the import volume index leads to an increase in food security in Algeria, as each 1% increase, leads to an increase in food availability of 0.0071%. This is acceptable because imports complement domestic production and maintain the stability

of food availability, which supports the food security index. As we know, domestic production is not sufficient to cover domestic demand, and to fill this gap, the state resorts to importing from global markets.

The second threshold: where the ratio of rural to total population is between 53.81% and 44%, which translates into an increase in migration from rural to urban areas. This represents a moderate to high level of rural-urban migration. At this threshold, the results show that the increase in migration has a negative impact on the food production index (FPI), which is an indication of a relative deterioration in food security. For every 1% increase in rural migration, the food production index decreases by 0.2158%, which is statistically significant at the 5% level. An increase in rural migration leads to a decrease in the labour force in the agricultural sector, in addition to the neglect or inefficient use of much agricultural land. This, in turn, leads to a decline in local agricultural production, which weakens self-sufficiency indicators and deepens the food gap. This is what happened in Algeria, especially during the black decade.

We also note that the inflation index (INF) has a negative impact on food security. This impact is logical in the Algerian economy, as a 1% increase in inflation leads to a 0.014% decrease in the food production index. The acceleration of rural migration often coincides with increased urban demand for food, exacerbating price fluctuations and increasing the cost of living, especially in the absence of effective support mechanisms or sustainable urban food planning. Inflation in agricultural input prices may also discourage many farmers from expanding their production or investing in the sector, which negatively affects local food supply.

It also appears that the impact of the agricultural land area (ALA) ratio plays a positive role in supporting food production, reaching 0.56. This decline reflects the beginning of agricultural land erosion, especially in areas surrounding major cities, as a result of urban expansion linked to migration. This leads to the loss of food production capacities that were previously vital, such that for every 1% increase in agricultural land, the food production index rises by 0.56%.

Third threshold: Where the ratio of rural to total population is between 44% and 33.9%, this translates into an increase in migration from rural to urban areas compared to the previous threshold. At this threshold, we observe that rural migration has a strong negative impact on food security, such that for every 1% increase in migration from rural to urban areas, the food production index decreases by 0.63%, which is statistically significant at the 5% level. This indicates that intensive rural migration to cities has a direct and clear impact on reducing the agricultural sector's ability to continue to meet national food needs. This reflects the economic reality in Algeria, where recent decades have seen rapid urban expansion, coupled with a clear decline in agricultural activity, especially in areas that were once major sources of food production.

We also note that the impact of inflation at this threshold was weak, as a 1% increase in inflation leads to a 0.016% increase in the food production index, which seems illogical. However, this may be due to the fact that price increases have an indirect positive effect on production. At this stage, producers in the agricultural sector aim to increase their production in order to benefit from higher prices and increase their profits, which has a positive impact on food availability and thus increases food security. The reason may also be due to intensive government interventions to protect food security, such as supporting local production and raising the purchase prices of grains from producers, which encourages some farmers to return

to or improve agricultural production. In addition, we note that in light of increasing rural migration and its exacerbation, the government resorted to raising government subsidies and provided significant facilities for land reclamation, increased rural support, introduced rural housing grants, and supported desert farming. These measures had a significant impact on increasing cultivated agricultural areas. This led to an increase in agricultural production, which in turn had a positive impact on local production. This indicates that every small increase in cultivated areas can have a high return in light of demand pressure and the scarcity of local supply, such that every 1% increase in the percentage of cultivated land leads to a 1.09% increase in the food production index.

We also note that the Food Import Index (FII) had a negative impact, reflecting the worrying situation that reliance on imports did not contribute to improving local food production, but may have led to a slowdown in agricultural investment due to foreign competition, or created a kind of dependence on the international market. This negative impact also translates into fragility in Algerian food sovereignty and its dependence on global prices and geopolitical fluctuations, as a 1% increase in imports leads to a 0.071% decrease in food security.

The fourth threshold: where the ratio of rural to total population is less than 33.9%, which translates into a significant increase in migration from rural to urban areas, such that the rural population is less than one-third of the total population. At this threshold, we observe that rural migration has a very strong negative impact, such that for every 1% increase in migration from rural to urban areas, the food production index decreases by 0.74%, which is statistically significant at the 5% level. This highlights that the continued decline in the rural population to minimum levels leads to the almost complete disintegration of the agricultural production base. With this sharp decline in the rural labour force and the decrease in the effective use of agricultural land, the national capacity to produce food is weakened, creating a gradually widening food gap, which increases the fragility of national food security. This confirms that the erosion of the Algerian countryside has had a structurally damaging effect on food security, and that continuing in this direction without decisive intervention will deepen food dependency and increase food price volatility in the local market.

At this threshold, where migration from rural to urban areas is at its highest, the results show that inflation has a negative impact on food security, with a 1% increase in inflation leading to a 0.025% decrease in food availability. This effect clearly reflects the situation in Algeria, where rising consumer prices, especially for food, erode purchasing power, particularly among low-income groups in densely populated urban areas. This is what Algeria has experienced in recent years with the rapid rise in prices of basic commodities such as oil, milk, flour and vegetables, coinciding with high inflation rates that exceeded 9% in some periods. This situation has become more acute in large cities, where population pressure resulting from rural migration has led to increased demand for food and higher prices, thereby reducing food security levels among the population, especially given the limited government support during periods of crisis. We also note that increasing the area under cultivation has a significant positive impact on local agricultural production, thereby supporting food security in Algeria. For every 1% increase in cultivated area, food security increases by 2.41%. This demonstrates the strategic importance of cultivated land in ensuring national food security. Preserving agricultural land and using it effectively has a significant impact on increasing production and

providing food for citizens locally. In addition, the import volume index had a positive impact, with each 1% increase in the latter leading to a 0.073% increase in food availability. This positive impact may be due to the fact that, in light of the large-scale migration of rural populations and the resulting decline in the agricultural workforce, and with the state's continued support and incentives for land reclamation and utilisation and its support for desert agriculture, this labour shortage needs to be compensated with advanced technology through the import of harvesting machines, tractors, drip irrigation systems, fertilisers and improved seeds. As Algeria relies heavily on imports to provide these means, the increase in imports of these products can indirectly contribute to boosting local production and thus improving food security.

The results of the regression model with thresholds show that the model has high statistical significance, as $F - statistic = 477.21 > F_t^{0.05} = 2.56 \Leftrightarrow prob(F - statistic) = 0.0000 < 0.05$, which allows us to reject the null hypothesis and confirms that the independent variables explain a significant portion of the variation in the food production index. In addition, the coefficient of determination (R-squared) reached 0.9962, which indicates a high explanatory power of the model, as the independent variables in this model explain 99.62% of the changes in food security in Algeria.

3.4. Estimated model diagnostics:

Table 2: Diagnostic test results

Test	Test type	Statistic	Calculated statistic	Tabulated statistic	Probability value
Autocorrelation	Breusch-Godfrey	F-statistic	0.7143	4.17	0.4041
		Chi square	1.1442	3.841	0.2848
Homoscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	F-statistic	1.3416	1.84	0.2219
		Chi square	23.1388	30.144	0.2319
Normal distribution	Jarque-Bera	Jarque-Bera	0.3691	5.99	0.8314
Functional form of the model	Ramsey-Reset	F-statistic	0.7359	4.17	0.3971

Source: Prepared by researchers.

From Table 2, we observe the following:

- Testing for the absence of autocorrelation between errors: Since the calculated value of chi square is less than the tabulated value $\chi_c^2 = 1.1442 < \chi_t^2 = 3.841 \Leftrightarrow prob(\text{Chi square}) = 0.2848 > 0.05$, which is confirmed by Fisher test, where we observe that $F_c^{0.05} = 0.7143 < F_t^{0.05} = 4.17$, which is demonstrated by the Durbin-Watson test, where we observe that $DW = 1.7629 \subset [DU = 1.73, 2]$. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis H_0 and reject the alternative hypothesis H_1 , which means that the estimated model does not contain the problem of autocorrelation between errors.

- Test of homoscedasticity: Since the calculated value of chi square is less than the tabulated value $\chi_c^2 = 23.1388 < \chi_t^2 = 30.144 \Leftrightarrow prob(\text{Chi square}) = 0.2319 > 0.05$, which is confirmed by Fisher test, where we observe that $F_c^{0.05} = 1.3416 < F_t^{0.05} = 1.84$. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis H_0 and reject the alternative hypothesis H_1 . This means that the variance of errors in the estimated model is homogeneous (constant), i.e., the model does not suffer from the problem of homoscedasticity.

- Testing the normal distribution of errors: Since the calculated Jarque-Bera value is less than the tabulated value for chi-square $J - B = 0.3691 < \chi_t^2 = 5.99 \Leftrightarrow prob(\text{Chi square}) = 0.8314 > 0.05$, we accept the null hypothesis H_0 and reject the alternative hypothesis H_1 , i.e., the errors follow a normal distribution.

- Test of functional form of the model: Since the calculated Fisher's value is less than the tabulated value $F - statistic = 0.7359 < F_t^{0.05} = 4.17 \Leftrightarrow prob(F - statistic) = 0.3971 > 0.05$, we accept the null hypothesis H_0 and reject the alternative hypothesis H_1 . Therefore, we accept the symbolic representation of the model, i.e., the model specification is correct.

- Testing the structural change of the model (graphical representation of CUSUM and CUSUM of squares):

Figure 2: Structural stability test

Source: Prepared by researchers.

From the graph above, we can see that the cumulative sum (CUSUM) line stays within the confidence bands at a 5% significance level throughout the study period. This means that the model coefficients are stable, i.e., the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable has not changed structurally over the study period. Furthermore, the cumulative line (CUSUM of Squares line) within the limits at the 5% level indicates that the residual variance is stable over time, i.e., there are no significant changes in the residual variance (heteroskedasticity), suggesting that the model is stable in terms of error distribution. Therefore, the model is considered stable with no structural change and can be relied upon to explain the relationships between the estimated model variables.

4. Conclusion:

The study of the effects of rural migration on food security has revealed profound, complex and multidimensional negative repercussions. International experience has shown that the migration of people from rural areas to cities often leads to a decline in agricultural production as a result of a decline in the labour force, which weakens the ability of countries to achieve food self-sufficiency and causes an imbalance in the distribution of population and resources, which in turn has a negative impact on the ability of countries to achieve food self-sufficiency and enhance their food security in a sustainable manner.

The results obtained through our use of the threshold model show that demographic shifts, particularly the decline in the rural population, have direct and indirect effects on food production. The relationship between the rural population ratio (RUMIG) and the food production index (FPI) in Algeria during the period 1970–2023 is highly sensitive and asymmetrical, as it appears that the decline in the rural population ratio – i.e. increased migration to cities – is associated with a significant decline in national food production. This is consistent across different thresholds, but with varying degrees of severity. At the upper thresholds, where the rural population is relatively high (between 53.8% and 44%), the negative impact of migration on food security is present but less severe (coefficient -1.047). At the lowest threshold (RUMIG < 33.9%), where the proportion of the rural population is at its lowest, the impact of migration becomes more destructive to food production (coefficient -4.875), reflecting the structural collapse of the agricultural sector as a direct result of labour migration.

The impact of rural migration is not limited to the shortage of agricultural labour, but extends to the indirect negative impact of urban sprawl on fertile agricultural land surrounding major cities. Uncontrolled urban expansion in many provinces has led to the erosion of large areas of highly productive agricultural land, as in the Mitidja and Hamza plains, where agricultural land has been converted into housing and urban expansion due to demographic pressures. These results show that food security in Algeria is not only affected by technical factors such as production or climate, but also by demographic and social changes, the most important of which are rural exodus and the decline in the agriculturally productive population, in addition to the destruction of agricultural land adjacent to cities as a result of urban sprawl. From this perspective, the continuation of rural migration at its current rate could undermine efforts to achieve food self-sufficiency, this requires decision-makers to adopt balanced development policies that take into account the revitalisation of rural areas and the stabilisation of their populations, with strict legislation to protect agricultural land from uncontrolled urbanisation, as well as support for family farming and incentives for small and medium-sized agricultural projects.

Recommendations and proposals: In light of the findings of this study, and in order to enhance food security in Algeria, we propose the following:

- Developing an integrated development model that combines urban and rural areas to reduce the development gap and provide urban services in rural areas, thereby reducing the incentives for migration.

- Improve living conditions in rural areas (housing, health, education, infrastructure) to stem the flow of migration to cities, thereby helping to preserve the agricultural workforce and ensure the sustainability of food production.

Encouraging desert and irrigated agriculture in the south and high plateaus as new areas that can absorb displaced populations from the north and restore the national food balance.

- Halt the encroachment of construction on fertile agricultural land, particularly in the Mitidja and Hamza plains, and expand investment in currently unused agricultural areas.

- Diversify agricultural imports and direct them towards equipment and technologies that support production, while reducing imports of ready-made food products that undermine domestic production.

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6. Appendices:

Appendix (01): Results of the estimation of the model Thresholds, standard coefficients and elasticities of the estimated model

Dependent Variable: FPI					Scaled Coefficients			
Method: Discrete Threshold Regression					Date: 08/17/25 Time: 12:00			
Date: 08/17/25 Time: 11:56					Sample: 1970 2023			
Sample: 1970 2023					Included observations: 54			
Included observations: 54					Included observations: 54			
Selection: Trimming 0.15, Max. thresholds 5, Sig. level 0.05								
Threshold variable: RUMIG								
White heteroskedasticity-consistent standard errors & covariances								
No d.f. adjustment for covariances								
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Variable	Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	Elasticity at Means
RUMIG < 33.902999 -- 15 obs					RUMIG < 33.902999 -- 15 obs			
C	-224.1420	39.40692	-5.687883	0.0000	C	-224.1420	-3.214545	-1.194363
RUMIG	-4.875453	0.273322	-17.83775	0.0000	RUMIG	-4.875453	-2.018069	-0.745564
INF	-0.900007	0.368119	-2.444881	0.0198	INF	-0.900007	-0.077928	-0.025724
ALA	26.17186	2.271956	11.51952	0.0000	ALA	26.17186	6.499973	2.414856
FII	0.175906	0.047124	3.732837	0.0007	FII	0.175906	0.200449	0.073174
33.902999 <= RUMIG < 44.002999 -- 13 obs					RUMIG < 53.810999 -- 15 obs			
C	-30.29902	98.85130	-0.306511	0.7611	C	-30.29902	-0.414773	-0.139924
RUMIG	-3.750962	0.943503	-3.975570	0.0003	RUMIG	-3.750962	-1.985980	-0.667453
INF	0.771160	0.157815	4.886494	0.0000	INF	0.771160	0.071146	0.016013
ALA	13.98136	4.443146	3.146726	0.0034	ALA	13.98136	3.245099	1.094536
FII	-0.530379	0.187209	-2.833076	0.0077	FII	-0.530379	-0.230648	-0.071559
44.002999 <= RUMIG < 53.810999 -- 12 obs					RUMIG < -- 15 obs			
C	209.1272	49.77789	4.201207	0.0002	C	209.1272	2.783840	0.891484
RUMIG	-1.047086	0.253054	-4.137801	0.0002	RUMIG	-1.047086	-0.675462	-0.215850
INF	-0.193050	0.070871	-2.723977	0.0101	INF	-0.193050	-0.051946	-0.014210
ALA	8.030589	2.865553	2.802457	0.0083	ALA	8.030589	1.750634	0.560581
FII	0.102387	0.122996	0.832437	0.4110	FII	0.102387	0.031257	0.009718
53.810999 <= RUMIG -- 14 obs					RUMIG < -- 15 obs			
C	-31.06957	26.00047	-1.194962	0.2404	C	-31.06957	-0.435961	-0.154520
RUMIG	0.994224	0.550224	1.806942	0.0796	RUMIG	0.994224	0.813074	0.287910
INF	-0.168031	0.068236	-2.462505	0.0190	INF	-0.168031	-0.022944	-0.007101
ALA	-0.292539	0.531048	-0.550871	0.5853	ALA	-0.292539	-0.074521	-0.026369
FII	0.153538	0.055315	2.775693	0.0089	FII	0.153538	0.044602	0.007106
R-squared	0.996264	Mean dependent var	52.12961					
Adjusted R-squared	0.994177	S.D. dependent var	31.52439					
S.E. of regression	2.405669	Akaike info criterion	4.871651					
Sum squared resid	196.7663	Schwarz criterion	5.608311					
Log likelihood	-111.5346	Hannan-Quinn criter.	5.155752					
F-statistic	477.2197	Durbin-Watson stat	1.762977					
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000							

Appendix (02): Diagnostic tests for the estimated model

- LM test to detect the absence of autocorrelation between errors

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:
Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 1 lag

F-statistic	0.714396	Prob. F(1,33)	0.4041
Obs*R-squared	1.144240	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.2848

- Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for detecting homogeneity (stability) of variance
- Jarque-Bera test for detecting normal distribution of errors

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey
 Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	1.341693	Prob. F(19,34)	0.2219
Obs*R-squared	23.13880	Prob. Chi-Square(19)	0.2313
Scaled explained SS	8.955374	Prob. Chi-Square(19)	0.9742

- Ramsy

test for detecting the functional form of the model

Source: Prepared by researchers

Ramsey RESET Test
 Equation: EQ03
 Omitted Variables: Squares of fitted values
 Specification: FPI C RUMIG INF ALA FII @THRESH RUMIG

	Value	df	Probability
t-statistic	0.857880	33	0.3971
F-statistic	0.735958	(1, 33)	0.3971
Likelihood ratio	1.191062	1	0.2751